

Multi-Domain Resilient Networking Architectures

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Abstract—Segment routing is an emerging traffic engineering technique relying on MPLS label stacking to steer traffic using the source routing paradigm. Traffic flows are enforced through a given path by applying a specifically designed stack of labels (i.e., the *segment list*). Each packet is then forwarded along the shortest path toward the network element represented by the top label. Unlike traditional MPLS networks, segment routing maintains per-flow state only at the ingress node, no signaling protocol is required to establish new flows neither to change the routing of active flows. Thus, control plane scalability is greatly improved. Several segment routing use cases have been recently proposed. As an example, it can be effectively used to dynamically steer traffic flows on paths characterized by low latency values. However, it may also suffer from some potential issues. Indeed, deployed MPLS equipment typically supports a limited number of stacked labels. Therefore, it is important to define the proper procedures to minimize the required segment list depth.

This work is focused on two relevant segment routing use cases: dynamic traffic recovery and traffic engineering in multi-domain networks. Indeed, in both use cases, the utilization of segment routing can significantly simplify the network operation with respect to traditional IP/MPLS procedures. Original schemes are proposed in this paper and evaluated including a simulative analysis of the depth of the required segment lists. Moreover, an experimental demonstration is performed in a multi-layer testbed exploiting an SDN-based implementation of segment routing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Segment Routing (SR) has been recently proposed within IETF to provide traffic engineering (TE) by simplifying control plane operation [1]. SR is essentially an implementation of the source routing paradigm. A specific header, composed of a stack of Multi Protocol Label Switched (MPLS) labels (i.e., the *segment list*), is included in each transmitted packet by the source node so that the traffic flows are routed through the desired path. Therefore, the segment list is compatible with the standard MPLS data plane and consists in an ordered list of *segment* identifier. For instance, a segment can identify a network node (i.e., *node segment*), a specific node interface (i.e., *adjacency segment*) or a service to be applied to the traffic flow (i.e., *service segment*). Considering a segment list composed of node segments only, each intermediate node processes the top label in the segment list to determine the interface to be used for forwarding the packet, i.e., the interface along the shortest path toward the node represented by the top label.

In traditional IP/MPLS networks a signaling protocol (e.g., Resource ReserVation Protocol with Traffic Engineering extensions - RSVP-TE) is used every time a new traffic flow has

to be activated in the network and a detailed per-flow state is maintained in each node traversed by the established Label Switched

Path (LSP). Conversely, using SR, a signaling protocol is not required and per-flow state is maintained only at the ingress node, where the segment list is enforced. This approach significantly simplifies the control plane operation especially in multi-layer networks, where SR can eliminate the need to establish and maintain hierarchical instances of Generalized MPLS (GMPLS) LSPs [2]. Moreover, SR natively implements Equal Cost Multi Path (ECMP) aware routing, i.e., in case of multiple shortest paths toward the destination the traffic is automatically load balanced on a per-flow basis. This characteristic also simplifies the control plane operation where complex configuration are often required to properly deploy load balancing policies. On the other hand, SR introduces a header in every data packet (i.e., the segment list), thus the depth of the segment list should be kept limited because it reduces the available packets payload area and because commercial MPLS equipment typically supports a limited number of stacked labels [3].

Besides simplification of the control plane operation, other interesting SR use cases have been recently proposed [4]. First, by changing the segment list applied to a specific traffic flow, SR can be effectively used to dynamically steer traffic on the path characterized by the most suitable traffic engineering parameters, e.g., to dynamically avoid link congestion. Second, SR enables a straightforward implementation of *service function chaining* through the stacking of the aforementioned service segments [5]. Third, centralized implementation of OAM (i.e., operations, administration and maintenance) procedures have been also proposed by exploiting SR functionalities to overcome complex RSVP-TE signaling procedures required for establishing monitoring LSPs [6]. Finally, SR can be effectively used upon network failures to perform traffic recovery without involving the controller and without requiring signaling during the recovery process and to enable the deployment of effective interdomain TE solutions.

This paper proposes, implements and experimentally validates SR schemes for addressing dynamic traffic recovery and inter-domain TE solutions in multi-layer networks.

Regarding traffic recovery, a SR scheme is proposed to dynamically recover traffic flows disrupted by link or node failures minimizing the depth of the required segment list. Using SR, traffic recovery can be performed locally so that the traffic is re-directed by the node detecting the failure toward the destination node, which is well known to be more effective in resource utilization with respect to schemes exploiting detour towards the next and next-next hop, as deployed in today's IP/MPLS networks.

Regarding inter-domain TE, two schemes are proposed and compared to apply the SR concept in a multi-domain network scenario

where the source routing concept is not directly applicable since network state information of remote the stack (BOS).

domains is not available at the source node. Moreover, given the absence of signaling sessions in the data plane, SR enables the scalable concatenation of multi-domain paths, overcoming the limitations and inter-operability issues of RSVP-TE stitching and nesting solutions, rarely deployed in practical scenarios. The proposed schemes are first evaluated by means of simulations in order to evaluate their performance and their scalability in terms of segment list depth. Moreover they are experimentally validated in a testbed deploying the SR approach in a Software Defined Networking (SDN) environment.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

Dynamic restoration is a well investigated topic in both optical and multi-layer (e.g., IP over WDM) network scenarios [7], [8]. However, most previous work considers the utilization of the distributed GMPLS control plane that features some important drawbacks due to possible contention among different signaling sessions [9]. From this point of view, recovery schemes based on the emerging SDN control plane can provide significant benefits if the centralized controller is properly exploited [10], [11].

Several recovery schemes have been proposed for implementation in Ethernet and IP/MPLS networks using the SDN approach and OpenFlow protocol. Specifically, the authors of [12]–[14] design restoration schemes for carrier grade Ethernet networks where the switch detecting the failure notifies the controller about the topology change. Then, the controller installs the backup paths in the data plane. In [15] a recovery mechanism is proposed based on path protection, where backup paths are computed and installed before the failure occurrence, thus not involving the controller upon failure. Finally, [16] proposes local traffic redirection from the point of failure to the destination. Also this mechanism does not involve the controller upon failure. However, all the aforementioned schemes may suffer from scalability issues. Indeed, if not involving the controller in the recovery mechanism, those methods require a number of backup flow entries in the nodes that is dependant on the number of working flows established in the network. Conversely, by exploiting SR, local traffic recovery can be enabled using a number of backup flow entries that does not depend on the number of flows established in the network.

Regarding multi-domain traffic engineering, the first solutions proposed for GMPLS-based optical and multi-layer networks were based on Border Gateway Protocol (BGP) [17], [18]. However, not advertising actual resource availability, BGP does not allow effective inter-domain path computation. To address this issue, the Path Computation Element (PCE) architecture has been extended to support inter-domain path computation using a distributed communication process among PCEs [19]. Later, the Hierarchical PCE (HPCE) architecture has been introduced where a Parent PCE (pPCE) coordinates the inter-domain path computation process [20]. More recently, the inclusion of intra-domain information directly at the pPCE has been proposed [21], [22], where such information is provided to the pPCE by resorting to recent BGP extensions [23]. However, this solution is not easily applicable in a multi-provider

scenario because of confidential information that should be shared at the pPCE.

Multi-domain TE solutions have been proposed using also the SDN control plane [24]–[26]. However, SDN control plane does not provide specific benefits in terms of multi-domain TE with respect to GMPLS/PCE. Indeed, in both cases the routing procedures are centralized: at the network controller or at the PCE, respectively.

Focusing on SR, even though standardization is rapidly evolving [1], [27], there has been a limited research work within the academic community. Authors of [28] proposed to combine the benefits of SR with those of a SDN control plane. The work in [29] implemented SR in carrier grade Ethernet networks including experimental and simulation studies. Algorithms to compute the segment list of a given path are proposed in [3], [30]. The work in [31] reports an achievable reduction of up to an order of magnitude in the state maintained in routers by using SR instead of RSVPTE. Several works including [32]–[34] detail experimental implementations and evaluations of the SR architecture.

The only proposals for implementing dynamic recovery using SR are [35] and our previous work [36]. In the scheme proposed by the authors of [35] backup paths are computed at the controller after failure occurrence. Conversely, [36] proposes a procedure, similar to MPLS fast reroute [37], to locally re-route disrupted traffic flows around a faulted network element without involving the central controller. The scheme proposed in this paper enhances the one in [36] by implementing the recovery from the point of failure to the destination node thus minimizing the segment list depth. Finally, at the best of our knowledge, no SR solution has been proposed in literature to deploy TE policies.

III. TRAFFIC RECOVERY USING SEGMENT ROUTING

Current recovery solutions deployed in IP/MPLS networks (e.g., fast reroute) exploit detour towards the next or the next-next hop. However, it is well known that recovering the traffic by redirecting it directly to the destination node is a more effective solution in terms of resource utilization. Thus, the target of the proposed SR recovery mechanism (i.e., SR-FAILOVER scheme) is to re-route the traffic affected by the failure from the node detecting the failure up to the destination (i.e., the node indicated in the deepest label of the segment list). To this extent the SR-FAILOVER scheme proposes to use a *primary forwarding table* in each node and a number of *failover forwarding tables*. Specifically, one failover table is required for each interface of the node. Primary and failover tables include N entries, where N is the number of node segments belonging to the routing domain. Thus, the number of required entries does not depend on the number of flows established in the network.

Using the SR-FAILOVER scheme, when the output port indicated in the primary table for a specific ingress label is down the backup actions in the primary table are executed. By applying the backup actions, the node first pops all the labels in the segment list except the deepest label (i.e., the bottom of the stack), then the packet processing is passed on to the proper failover table, see Fig. 1c. The actions to be executed within the failover tables depend on the value of the bottom label. Specifically, for each label the failover table enforces the utilization of a loop free backup path. To do this, a number of push

actions may be required before forwarding the packet if a loop free alternate path is not directly available from the node detecting the failure. Backup paths are computed on the updated network topology where the failed link is removed and encoded with a segment list that exploits the primary tables in subsequent nodes to reach the destination with a strict path.

To implement the proposed scheme each node has to be properly configured during network initialization so that, when a node physically detects a failure of a connected interface, it is able to locally redirect the traffic on the proper backup path. The network initialization can be performed in a distributed way using a properly extended Interior Gateway Protocol (IGP) [1] or exploiting a centralized SR controller that continuously monitors the network topology and enforces the required flow table entries in the network nodes [33].

This work considers the adoption of a SR controller since it is more consistent with the SDN approach and it easily enables the configuration of multiple forwarding tables as required by the SR-FAILOVER scheme. The SR controller includes a Traffic Engineering Database (TED) including network topology and resource utilization information that are used for path computation purpose. Specifically, the SR controller exploits the SDN approach to program the data plane using the OpenFlow protocol [33]. First, primary and failover tables are properly initialized. Then, when a new traffic flow has to be activated the ingress node can simply apply the destination node segment or asks the SR controller. In this latter case, the controller replies with a specific segment list to enforce a path that is centrally computed considering all the required constraints. In any case, the SR controller is not involved in the recovery mechanism so that recovery time is minimized.

Fig. 1 illustrates the required flow tables configuration to deploy the SR-FAILOVER scheme in the depicted sample topology. Specifically, Fig. 1a illustrates all the primary tables of the nodes belonging to the network topology illustrated in Fig. 1b. The flows installed in the primary tables simply implement shortest path routing toward each network node considering ECMP load-balancing. For instance, at node B two ECMPs are available toward node E , therefore load balancing is applied using port 2 and port 3.

The blue solid line in Fig. 1b represents a working traffic flow traversing the path $p_{11}^{-} = \{A, B, D, E\}$, this path encoded

p_{11}^{-} with the segment list $SL = \{D, E\}$. Thus,

node B receives the traffic with label D and forwards the traffic toward node D using interface 2. In case of failure of this interface, label D is popped then the switch is redirected to failover table 2 that implements the routing on a topology where the link $B-D$ is pruned. Specifically, Fig. 1c illustrates all the failover tables configured at node B , in the case of p_{11}^{-} the backup path is $\{A, B, C, E\}$, i.e., blue dashed line in Fig. 1b. Since the bottom of the stack is label E , traffic is simply forwarded on interface 3 without requiring further actions. Conversely, for path $p_{12}^{-} = \{A, B, D\}$, i.e., green solid line in Fig. 1(b) the backup path is $\{A, B, C, E, D\}$, i.e., green dashed line in Fig. 1b. In this case the destination is D and, to assure a loop free route, a new label is required to be pushed by node B (i.e., label E) before forwarding it on interface 3. This way, at node C , the traffic matches the desired backup path in the primary table and it is correctly forwarded using interface 2.

The SR-FAILOVER scheme as described in the previous

Fig. 3. Statistical distribution: percentage of backup paths encoded with a specific segment list depth in Pan European topology.

Fig. 4. Statistical distribution: percentage of backup paths encoded with a specific segment list depth in BRITE topology.

paragraph considers single link failures. However, it can be easily extended to node failures. Indeed, it is sufficient to initialize the failover tables computing the backup paths on the topology by pruning all the links connected to the failed node. As an example, if node A detects a failure on interface 1 the backup paths should be computed assuming the failure of node B , i.e., pruning bidirectional links $A-B$, $C-B$, and $D-B$ from the network topology.

IV. MULTI-DOMAIN TE USING SEGMENT ROUTING

This section proposes two schemes based on SR to enable effective TE in a multi-domain networks, i.e., *end-to-end* segment routing (e2e-SR) and *per-domain* segment routing (pd-SR). Also in this case, the proposed schemes can be implemented in a distributed way by using proper BGP extension [1] or, as considered in this work, in a scenario where each domain relies on a dedicated SR controller. However, since the advertisement of node segment identifiers is limited within the domain boundaries, the SR controller of each domain is not aware of intra-domain topology of other domains, i.e., the stored TED includes only information of the specific domain. Therefore, a communication procedure among SR controllers should be used to perform effective inter-domain TE.

Both proposed schemes leverage on a two-way communication session established among the SR controllers of the traversed domains. However, the two schemes use a different procedure to determine the segment list to be applied to data packets. In e2e-SR a segment list with end-to-end validity is enforced by the source node and never integrated along the path to the destination node. Conversely, in the pd-SR scheme the segment list is integrated at each ingress border node traversed by the traffic flow. In both cases the sequence of border nodes to be traversed is considered to be known in advance, e.g., it can be provided by the Network Management System (NMS) or computed by a hierarchical controller such as in the standardized HPCE architecture [18].

Fig. 2a details the e2e-SR scheme procedure in a network including three domains (i.e., $D1$, $D2$, and $D3$). When a traffic request (from node A to node F) is generated by the NMS, SR controller of domain $D1$ forwards the request to the controller of subsequent domains through the assigned sequence of domains. When the request reaches the controller of the destination domain (i.e., SR controller of domain $D3$ in Fig. 2a), it computes a path from its ingress border node (i.e., E in Fig. 2a) to the destination node F and forwards the computed segment list to the upstream SR controller. Intermediate controllers apply the same procedure where the forwarded segment list is obtained by stitching the segment list received by the downstream controller with the segment list computed locally. This way, when the SR controller of domain $D1$ receives the reply it is able to build up the end-to-end segment list and to properly configure the source node forwarding table, thus enforcing the end-to-end segment list to the incoming packets belonging to the flow.

Fig. 2b details the pd-SR scheme procedure, that is specifically designed to provide shorter segment lists and to preserve confidentiality of internal topology information. In this case, the SR controllers do not forward the computed segment list to the upstream controller, instead they just forward a *virtual* label (i.e., X and Y respectively for $D2$ and $D3$ in Fig. 2b) and contextually configure the ingress border node to properly process packets that will arrive using that virtual label. In Fig. 2b node C is configured so that, for those packets using label X , the segment list is set to $D - E - Y$; whereas node E is configured so that for packets using label Y the segment list is set to F .

V. SIMULATIVE AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Segment routing recovery

To assess the scalability of the SR-FAILOVER scheme, in terms of *segment list depth* (SLD), two network topologies are considered in a simulated environment: a Pan European network including 27 nodes and 55 bidirectional links, and a topology generated with BRITE [38] including 150 nodes and 300 bidirectional links. In both topologies, the SLD is computed for a set of backup paths with SR-FAILOVER scheme and with the scheme described in [36] where backup paths are computed from the point of failure to the node identified by the next label in the segment list. A single backup path is computed for each link failure that can affect every shortest path in the network. This way, 6,332 and 198,270 backup paths are considered for the Pan European and the BRITE topologies, respectively.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the obtained distribution of the SLD. In the Pan European topology, Fig. 3, the SR-FAILOVER scheme achieves

an average SLD of 1.45 with respect to the average value 2.01 obtained using the reference scheme [36]. In the BRITE network, Fig. 4, the achieved SLD is 1.63 with respect to 2.15 obtained using the reference scheme [36]. Also it is shown that, for both topologies, using the SR-FAILOVER scheme 95% of the backup paths use a segment list of 1 or 2 labels, whereas this percentage is about 70% using the reference scheme.

The SR-FAILOVER scheme has been implemented in an experimental testbed using an SDN controller and five OpenFlow switches. In the switches, the primary forwarding table uses the *Group Table* OpenFlow feature to enable the monitoring of the interfaces status and support a backup list of actions to be applied when the primary forwarding interface is down. Nodes have been implemented within Intel Core 4 servers (CPU 2.40 GHz, Linux kernel 3.13) equipped with four Gb/s Ethernet interfaces and running OpenvSwitch version 2.4.0, supporting MPLS-based forwarding. OpenFlow 1.3 has been utilized for the communication between the nodes and the controller. The controller has been implemented, on a dedicated server, by extending the SDN RYU controller [39]. Commercially available ROADMs equipped with 10Gb/s OTN muxponders have been connected to nodes for implementing the optical transport plane of the multilayer network.

The aforementioned hardware has been utilized to realize the network topology represented in Fig. 1b where the two traffic flows along paths p_1 and p_2 are established. Fig. 5a illustrates the testbed topology visualized by the web-based Ryu Topology Viewer. The datapath id (i.e., *dpid*) of each node is used as node segment identifier in the enforced segment lists. The *ping* application is used from host A (i.e., IP address 10.0.34.1) to both destination hosts B and C (i.e., IP addresses 10.0.35.1 and 10.0.38.1). Initially, no failure is present on the network. The two traffic flows are steered using the segment list as described in Fig. 1b. Specifically, the Wireshark capture in Fig. 5b is executed on port 2 of node with *dpid* 1002, it shows that packets directed to host B use a segment list composed of a single label, i.e., 1004. Then a failure is generated by physically disconnecting the cable from port 4 of node with *dpid* 1004. The failure holds from time 12:58:05 to time 12:58:21; during this period no packets are routed on this interface. The capture in Fig. 5c is executed on port 3 of node with *dpid* 1002, it shows that during the failure traffic to host B uses this port and includes segment list composed of two labels i.e., 1001, 1004.

To accurately evaluate the recovery time required by the SR-FAILOVER scheme, the aforementioned failure have been repeated more than 200 times. The *ping* has been used to generate a packet every 2 ms, so that the traffic hole generated by the occurrence of the failure can be easily measured by parsing the Wireshark capture of the packets by host B . Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the obtained recovery time (243 samples) where the average value is 13.1 ms.

B. Segment Routing in multi-domain networks

The scalability of the proposed e2e-SR and pd-SR schemes has been evaluated in terms of SLD in a simulated environment. The reference multi-domain topology reported in [22] is considered including 75-nodes, 292-links, and 9-domains. The SLD is evaluated for all the paths within one hop from the shortest path for all the node pairs in the network, thus considering a total of more than 137,000 paths. For each

given path, the SR controller of each domain uses the algorithm adopted in [33] to compute the encoding segment list.

Fig. 7 illustrates the achieved distribution of the maximum SLD for all the considered paths. Using the e2e-SR scheme, the maximum SLD along a given path is always registered at the source node; conversely, using the pd-SR scheme the maximum SLD can be registered in any of the traversed border nodes that perform the mapping of virtual labels.

Fig. 6. Statistical distribution: recovery time [ms] measured in the experimental testbed.

Fig. 7. Statistical distribution: maximum segment list depth values for the two schemes considering multi-domain network topology illustrated in [22].

The figure shows that pd-SR scheme is able to encode 60% of the paths with a segment list composed of 1, 2, or 3 labels, while e2e-SR encodes less than 12% of the paths within the three labels. The achieved SLD average values of e2e-SR and pd-SR are 5.34 and 3.36, respectively. In the example represented in Fig. 2, the e2e-SR scheme provides a maximum depth of 5 (applied at source node *A*); whereas the pd-SR scheme provides a maximum depth of 3 (applied at node *A* and at the border node of domain *D2*).

To validate the proposed pd-SR scheme the same experimental testbed described above has been utilized but in the configuration illustrated in Fig. 8. The network includes six Open vSwitch nodes divided in two domains. Each domain includes three nodes, moreover, two optical nodes are used to implement the inter-domain link that is

transparent to SR operation. SR controllers based on SDN RYU [39] have been properly extended to support the proposed multi-domain schemes.

Each node in Fig. 8 is shown with the specific forwarding table including the relevant entries. The labels are obtained from the node id adding the prefix 1000, the virtual label is randomly generated among unused labels. A traffic flow is configured from host *H2* to host *H1* with the pd-SR

Fig. 8. Experimental validation of the pd-SR scheme.

Fig. 9. Wireshark capture of the OFPT_FLOW_MOD message sent from the controller of domain *D2* to node 5.

scheme. Specifically, node 5 is configured by the domain 2 controller as ingress node including the entry toward *H1* with three associated actions: pushing of the assigned virtual label (push 1000632); pushing of the label of node 2 which is the ingress border node of domain 1 (push 10002); and forwarding of the packets along port 1 (out 1). The ingress border of domain 1 (node 2) is configured by domain 1 controller with one entry matching the virtual label, where the associated actions are: popping of the virtual label (pop), pushing of the node 1 label (push 10001), and forwarding of the packet along port 1 (out 1). The setup procedure has been performed 200 times achieving the average setup time of 3.4 ms.

Fig. 9 shows the Wireshark capture of the OpenFlow OFPT_FLOW_MOD message sent by the controller of domain 2

to configure the ingress node 5. The insets in Fig. 9 highlight the message fields containing the two used labels (i.e., the virtual label 1000632, and the label 10002 of node 2).

VI. CONCLUSION

Traffic recovery and multi-domain traffic engineering schemes based on segment routing have been proposed and demonstrated in a multi-layer SDN network.

Regarding the traffic recovery, simulation results showed that using the SR-FAILOVER scheme the wide majority of backup paths can be encoded with segment list of one or two labels. Experimental measurements reported an average recovery time of 13 ms. Such good performance confirm that segment routing is a strong candidate technology for effective traffic recovery. Moreover, given the absence of signaling sessions, it enables the scalable implementation of failover up to the destination node, which is well known to be more effective

in resource utilization with respect to schemes exploiting detour towards the next-next hop, as deployed in today's MPLS networks through fast reroute mechanism.

Regarding multi-domain traffic engineering, the two considered schemes have been compared in terms of provided segment list depth. Simulation results demonstrated that pd-SR scheme is able to significantly reduce the segment list depth with respect to the e2e-SR scheme. Experimental validation of the pd-SR scheme showed a configuration time of less than 4 ms for establishing a new inter-domain traffic flow. Also in this case, such good performance confirm that segment routing can be effectively adopted for multi-domain traffic engineering. Indeed, given the absence of signaling sessions between border nodes belonging to different domains, it enables the scalable concatenation of multi-domain paths, overcoming the limitations and inter-operability issues of RSVP-TE stitching and nesting solutions, rarely deployed in practical scenarios.

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